

PRELIMINARY TRAINING IN THE GAME OF VOLLEYBALL AND ITS ESSENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the development of technical preparation, organizing, their training, the aim and task of training, the aids of it.

Keywords: Training, technical preparation, initial teaching, preparation, special exercises, the methods of teaching.

Introduction

In addition to the development of physical education and mass sports in our country, the importance is paid to the development of large sports. Every year in our Republic, international and world-class prestigious competitions are held, which make young people more interested in sports. Our athletes have achieved high results by participating in the Asian, World and Olympic competitions and glorify the fame of our country. One of the ways to solve this problem is to redirect various types of targeted physical education programs to the maximum satisfaction of the needs of each student, to take into account as fully as possible the level of physical development and training of the learners. Unfortunately, although sports games, in particular volleyball, are widely developed, there are no high results in international competitions. As a volleyball academic discipline, all educational institutions are included in the curriculum, operating during the extracurricular and extracurricular hours.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Until now, a number of scientific studies have been carried out on the

problems of the theory and practice of physical education and sports, which highlight the issues of differentiated methodology for the use of sports games in groups of sports training of higher education institutions. L.R.Ayrapetyans, M.A.Godik,1991; Yu.D.Zheleznyak, 1994; M.C.Akhmatov, 2004. In addition V.A.Kobzev, 1996; N.A.Anashkina, 1998; A.Zelensky, 1998; V.P.In the scientific work of Guba, 2000 and others, the student laid out the scientific - theoretical and practical foundations and methods of using a differentiated approach to organizing the process of physical education of young people. Movement and play skills-passing the ball, receiving (defense), entering the ball into the game, striking, stumbling are mastered in the specified stages, using certain styles and tools, and improvement-is resurrected. This process is based on pedagogical, biopsychological and biomechanical laws.

Results The teaching process is a pedagogical process that requires great skill, professional training from a coach-teacher. But even so, training in the technique of performing an action (game qualification) is due to other significant reasons. Including the activity of the child, the number, quality of training, duration of duration, auxiliary technical equipment, the conditions of the place of training, the interest of the child, the wealth of movement, experience, etc. It is also necessary to say that the duration of mastering the technique of movement also depends on the family conditions of the child, his social and economic capabilities and his mental state.

The above information and factors to consider in the training process should take place from planning documents based on a certain methodological procedure. In addition, it is necessary to determine the internal mystical capabilities of the child, as well as the available factors, with the help of a selection program and exercises. The results obtained should serve as a supporting factor in the application of teaching methods, stages and technology.

The initial training process is carried out in several stages, and each of these stages includes its own style and tools. General developmental exercises are

applied to the player's physical perfection and bleaching of the movement skills and skills necessary for the player.

These include general physical, special physical, technical, tactical and Game training, with all exercises United in accordance with their direction, forming the main parts of the training's special training. Each type of preparation has its own leading factors with which the intended goal is achieved. At the same time, all types of preparations are inextricably linked with each other. For example, if the student is not physically well trained, he will not be able to do the striking technical exercise well in the attack. In this case, physical conditioning of the student is more useful than repeating the blow method many times. In the initial teaching, it is necessary to be guided step by step and based on the principle of teaching.

The first stage is acquaintance with the technique of movement to be studied. In this case, methods of telling, showing and explaining are used. The coach uses visual weapons along with the display, such as Motion Picture, Picture film, scheme, field layout, etc. The show should be accompanied by explanations. The first attempts of the coach-teacher form a primary sense of action in them.

The second stage is the study of the technique in a simplified state. Success in this learning phase depends in many cases on the correct selection of approach exercises. They should be close to the technique of the movement being studied according to the shape of their structure and capable of being performed by students. Movements with a complex structure, that is, an attack shot, are disassembled into the main zvenos that make it up. At this stage, control techniques are used such as command, guidance, vision and hearing, review progress, technical means, etc. and visual action techniques such as direct assistance from the coach - teacher, application of auxiliary equipment, impact force on the Information ball, accuracy of fall, light or voice marking will be of particular importance.

The third stage is to teach the technique in a complicated setting. The following are used in this: repetitive method, execution of movement in complex conditions, play and assessment style, joint style, circular exercises. The repetition style is the most basic at this stage. It is only repeated many times that the qualification is formed. Repetition in order to generate competence assumes the performance of exercises under different conditions to change the conditions of movement, gradually complicating. Even when tired, the exercises are performed, the joint and playing styles will be aimed at simultaneously bleaching the technique, solving the issues of growing special physical qualities, and improving the technical and tactical training and playing skills.

The fourth stage-envisages strengthening the action in the game process. In this, a method of interpreting the actions performed is used (pictures, tables, educational films, pictorial films), in the process of playing, techniques-tactical, special training tasks, game and competition methods are used.

Discussion

In preparatory and educational games, it is envisaged to study each method (qualification), improve and perfect it. The highest means of strengthening qualification is to compete. In volleyball, as in other sports, exercise is the main means of teaching. They are very diverse. Therefore, they are categorized by their role in solving the tasks set at a particular training stage. Such a categorization is based on the competition activities of volleyball players. In connection with this, the exercises are divided into two large groups, these are the main or competition and the auxiliary or training. The effectiveness of tools when teaching volleyball movements in many cases will directly depend on the methods of their application. Methods are selected and applied depending on the task set, the level of training of those involved, specific conditions.

Depending on the task set, it is possible to use exactly one tool in different styles and use it in different ways. In addition, in each type of preparation, the

sequence of tasks and types also has a certain logical connection. Tasks of one type of preparation change qualitatively, laying the groundwork for the next type of preparation. For example, preparatory exercises express the general structure of the studied technical method. Approach exercises act as a bridge in the transition from special physical training to technical training. Technical exercises built on a certain level of complexity help to form tactical skills. On this basis, individual tactical actions are subsequently studied.

Conclusion

The main movement in volleyball consists of walking, running, walking on a side step, with a back, standing on a step, jumping. In most cases, movements are interpreted as not difficult, and they are not given enough attention. This is a misconception. Because the choice of position and location for the player to perform various actions directly affects the effect of the action to be performed. Therefore, it is necessary to pay close attention to the training of movements. The correct Organization of the initial training process by the coach provides the basis for the effective formation of such important tasks as ensuring the continuity of the national teams of the country and the cultivation of qualified Sports Reserves.

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